

Creating a Virtual Platform “Sekhi” by Mapping Transport Systems to Facilitate Sharing Community

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PROBLEM

A need to make the existing society to focus on sustainable travelling by creating a sharing platform with their existing resources.

APPROACH

Creating a virtual mapping platform “Sekhi” of transport systems and then enabling a sharing system in that virtual platform.

SEKHI

Sekhi, is a platform based on virtual mapping of system entities of transport systems. Entities are all modes of transport like cars, bikes and other vehicles. The virtual mapping is enabled by locks in system entities. We are designing a business model for “Sekhi” and analyzing the multitude usage of the virtual platform in our master thesis.

Main idea was built upon looking on how could the existing transport system built up to a virtual mapping arena and used sustainably thereafter. The most common entity that could be modified and utilized with respect to technology change and adaptability is the locks present in all modes of transportation. Present scenario in advancement of locks is having smart locks with geo-tracking systems and sensors, the system usage of the transport entity could be maximized. This maximized usage could be translated into a virtual platform where all entities become actors and these actors (cars or bikes) could be shared in system for a sustainable life. Thereby creating a sharing platform with the existing transport system resources without creating any infrastructure change.

Present system of creating a bike sharing is to invest in infrastructure whereas not using existing bikes. And car sharing system is where people manually enter about the availability of cars for sharing, but what if car being the main entity itself says that it is available to be shared. Sekhi enables all these drawbacks in present system to be fulfilled.

Sekhi could be further connected with freight transportation in urban area, thereby creating a link between personal transportation and freight transportation. Sharing platform could be used for delivery of goods when the transit locations are identified by the platform. During the commute, goods could be delivered without additional transportation need, thereby decreasing the traffic in the urban area.

Value Proposition

- Anti-theft module for bikes and bike sharing system
- Combined Transportation Card (Car + Bikes + Public Transportation + Taxis)
- Crowd Sourcing Urban Delivery
- Boxes in bus stops activated using smart locks and used for delivery, transit of goods